

BALLISTIC IMPACT RESPONSE FOR TWO-STEP BRAIDED THREE-DIMENSIONAL TEXTILE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the ballistic impact response of 3-D two-step braided textile composite struck by a 36.1 gm hemi-spherical tip-ended rigid cylindrical projectile. A series of quasi-static punch tests has been conducted in order to investigate the progressive damage modes of target and to obtain the punch load-displacement relationship. In addition, a pneumatic launcher is used to propel the projectile with incident velocities ranging from 70 to 170 m/sec. The ballistic limit is experimentally determined to be near 74.1 m/sec. Commercially available finite element code (MARC) is incorporated with a constitutive relationship for 3-D two-step braided composite structure and the proposed static penetration model to simulate the dynamic impact response. Descriptions of the constitutive modeling of three-dimensional braided composite and the effect of penetration on the degradation of elastic stiffness for the specimen studied here will be presented in a separate paper. An energy consideration is applied to predict the projectile's residual (or terminal) velocity and ballistic limit. Numerical simulated result for projectile terminal velocities based on both the static and dynamic elastic properties is to be reported.

INTRODUCTION

Developments of textile technology gave rise to novel methods of three-dimensional fiber reinforced braided textile preforms⁽¹⁾. Textile composites with three-dimensional reinforced woven or braided preform were reported to be able to exhibit enhanced inter-laminar surfaces characteristics, better through-thickness stiffness and strength, and improved damage tolerance. Ko and Hartman⁽²⁾ reported that braided composite possesses highest damage resistance compared to that for 3-D(XYZ) and 2-D(XY) orthogonally woven fabric composites by using a drop tower impact tester. Gong and Sankar⁽³⁾ used an instrumented impact pendulum and a projectile gas gun to study the impact response and related damage tolerance of three-dimensional braided graphite/epoxy composite experimentally. They reported that braided composite shows better damage tolerance than a quasi-isotropic laminate with about the same bending stiffness in the primary direction in either static test or impact test. The impact damage patterns and the factors which affect the extent and modes of impact damage were also experimentally examined.

When we design a suitable light-weight protective structure subjected to ballistic impact loading, it would be important to understand the perforation condition for composite structures in question. Only a limited amount of work is found to analytically model the penetration/perforation behavior of composite laminates and to predict the ballistic limit for laminated structures, and it seems that no research work was published to analytically model the penetration/perforation conditions and to predict the terminal velocity of projectile and ballistic limit for 3-D reinforced braided textile composite. Therefore, a series of impact tests is conducted in this work in order to study the penetration/perforation condition of 3-D two-step braided glass/epoxy textile composite target struck by a 36.1 g hemi-spherical tip-ended rigid cylindrical penetrator. Similar to the ballistic impact modeling for graphite/epoxy and plain woven glass/epoxy laminates reported previously by Sun, et al.^(4,5) and Jenq, et al.⁽⁶⁾, respectively, the quasi-static punch tests are conducted here to examine the punch load-displacement relation and to characterize the penetration process for 3-D two-step braided textile composite. The quasi-static penetration model developed in this paper is

incorporated into the commercially available finite element code (MARC) as the penetration criteria to analyze dynamic impact response. The constitutive relationship for 3-D two-step braided composite^(7,8,9) and the modified Hertz contact law⁽¹⁰⁾ are also provided as user supplied subroutines in the finite element analysis. Descriptions of the constitutive modeling of three-dimensional braided composite and the effect of penetration on the degradation of elastic stiffness for the specimen studied here will be presented in a separate paper. Energy balance consideration is adopted to predict the ballistic limit. Comparison between the predicted ballistic limit and that found from tests is to be reported. In addition, the test determined and code predicted projectile residual (or terminal) velocities after perforation are examined. Due to rate-sensitive nature of glass/epoxy composites^(11,12,13), effect of variation of dynamic elastic moduli on the predicted projectile terminal velocity and ballistic limit is also studied numerically in this work.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND TEST RESULT

Two-step braiding technique⁽¹⁾ is adopted here to fabricate three-dimensional fiber preform and a vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (RTM) method is then used to manufacture the braided composite targets. Uni-directional E-glass fiber roving (Taiwan Glass Co. Ltd.) is used as axial and braider yarns to fabricate preform. Textile preform is infiltrated by an epoxy resin system composed of Araldite LY564 and HY2954 (Ciba-Geigy). The basic mechanical properties of matrix and the axial and braider fiber yarns are listed in Table 1. A fiber volume of about 0.45 is determined for the specimen manufactured. The thickness and width of these rectangular braided composite specimens are 3.6 and 25.1 mm, respectively. Table 2 shows the geometrical parameters of E-glass fiber preform used to calculate the mechanical properties of two-step braided specimen. Specimen is rigidly clamped along both ends with a span of 80 mm on an MTS tester in order to perform quasi-static punch test. During tests, a hemi-spherical tip-ended cylindrical rigid penetrator with a length and diameter of 100 and 12.7 mm, respectively, is used and the stroke rate of the penetrator is controlled at 0.125 mm per second. The purpose of performing these punch tests is to characterize the progressive damage mechanism and to obtain the punch load-displacement curve in order to characterize the penetration process for dynamic analysis. Similar processes used to predict the ballistic limit of graphite/epoxy laminate and plain woven glass/epoxy laminated composite have been reported by Lee and Sun⁽⁴⁾ and Jenq, et al.⁽⁶⁾, respectively.

Three typical load-displacement curves measured from quasi-static punch tests are plotted in Figure 1. Upon examining these dotted curves, it reveals that punch curves are reproducible and preserve a specific pattern. The basic pattern possesses physical meaning related to damage modes of braided composite due to quasi-static penetration by a hemi-spherical tip-ended rigid indenter, and it can be represented by the curve shown in Figure 2. There are seven checkpoints (i.e. point O, A, B, C, D, E and F) marked in Figure 2 for convenience. For a specimen loaded from point O to A, a nearly linear relationship between load and displacement is observed. No major damage mode is detected except very tiny matrix cracks found in the area under contact. If the loading level is higher than that for checkpoint A, the slopes of load-displacement curves shown in Figure 2 decrease indicating that matrix cracks start to propagate in the specimen. When specimen is loaded along loading path BC, the fibers located close to contact surface start to break progressively (in addition to matrix breakage) and it results in load descending as the stroke of penetrator increases. If this hemi-spherical indenter is further pressed downward, the damage area containing broken fibers continuously increases and results in extensive damage in the specimen. Therefore, the corresponding structural stiffness is further decreased for loading path CD. As the punch deeply penetrates into the target along loading path DE, the remaining intact fibers (containing both axial and braider yarns), located near to the distal surface of specimen, fracture and the broken fibers are pushed in the direction of penetrator motion out of the distal surface of target. Current load-displacement pattern is different from that found for laminated composite specimens reported previously, and no delamination phenomenon has been observed as we expected. At checkpoint E, the tip of the penetrator is about to exit from the distal surface of target. A nearly constant frictional force between the penetrator and target is observed from the loading path EF. Notice that if we compare the punch load-displacement curves shown in Figure 2 and that reported by Lee and Sun⁽⁵⁾ and Jenq, et al.⁽⁸⁾, no abrupt decreasing loading representing the major delamination damage mode is observed here. Furthermore, no obvious transition region for friction is observed since the plugging phenomenon does not prevail in the current study utilizing a hemi-spherical penetrator. Photographs of an undamaged specimen and a quasi-statically punched specimen will be presented in a separate paper⁽¹⁴⁾.

Eight high speed impact tests are also conducted in order to examine the impact damage of two-step braided textile composite and to determine the residual (or terminal) velocity and the ballistic

limit of specimens struck by a hemi-spherical tip-ended cylindrical rigid projectile with a length of 38.7 mm and weighing 36.1 g. The diameter of penetrator is 12.7 mm, which is the same as the diameter of indenter used in the quasi-static punch tests. A pneumatic gun is used to propel the projectile against targets with incident velocities ranging from 70 to 170 m/sec. The ballistic limit is experimentally determined to be near 74.1 m/sec. Both the projectile incident and terminal velocities are detected during tests. A schematic drawing of the dynamic impact test system is referred to previous published paper⁽⁶⁾. The major damage pattern found from the impacted specimens is dominated by indentation, matrix cracking (including resin pocket matrix damage), broken of axial and braider fiber yarns, and broken fibers pulled outward. These damage pattern is similar to that found from the quasi-static penetrated specimens. Based on test result, the dynamic impact damaged area is close to that found from quasi-static test result if the projectile incident velocity is approximately less than 110 m/sec. However, for higher impact velocities ranging from 110 to 170 m/sec, the impact damaged zone extend outward considerably. According to test result, the estimated ballistic limit shown in the fourth column of Table 3 is calculated based on the principle of conservation of energy for a rigid penetrator. Upon examining the estimated ballistic limit listed in Table 3, it reveals that the averaged estimated ballistic limit is 79 m/sec for test no. DB02, DB03 and DB04. This value is close to test determined ballistic limit of 74.1 m/sec. However, the estimated value increases as the incident velocity is increased. This discrepancy seems to be resulted from the fact that damage region is increased when target is impacted at projectile's incident velocity higher than 110 m/sec.

The yarn cross-sections of two-step braided rectangular specimen after adding matrix and consolidation can be assumed to be flattened⁽⁸⁾ as shown in Figure 3. The axial yarn cross-section is depend on its location in the fabric shown as the darkened area in Figure 6 for a [12,4] braided structure. Here [m,n] notation is used to describe the arrangement of m columns by n rows of axial yarns located in the cross-section boundary of a braid, and the axial and thickness directions of sample are plotted along x- and z-axis, respectively⁽¹⁾. In order to simplify the modeling process for computing target's elastic moduli for subsequent finite element analysis, the cross-sections of specimen can further be divided into four unit cells (i.e. unit cell 1 to 4 shown in Figure 3) in general. For current application, the [13,2] braided rectangular plate specimens are used. Elastic properties in each unit cell of 2-step braided composites can be predicted based on the fiber and matrix properties and the three-dimensional fiber architecture^(8,9). In addition, the global system compliance matrix for assumed homogeneous and isotropic matrix material can be obtained simply. The average stiffness matrix method used by Byun and Chou^(7,9) is then adopted to predict the elastic properties for the [13,2] two-step braided composite. Using the data given in Tables 1 and 2 which provide the geometrical and basic material parameters for current analysis, the computed elastic properties for unit cells one, two and four are presented in Reference (14). The difference between test determined apparent axial elastic modulus and the model predicted value, based on those computed elastic moduli for unit cell 1, 2 and 4 and their corresponding volume rations, is within 15 %. This discrepancy may be resulted from that (1) during braiding process some fiber yarns are damaged and (2) current simplified modeling slightly deviates from real specimen's geometrical relationship. Detailed descriptions of the constitutive modeling of three-dimensional braided composite and the effect of penetration on the degradation of elastic stiffness for the specimen studied here will be presented in a separate paper.

STATIC AND DYNAMIC SIMULATED RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The ballistic limit of 2-step braided textile composite specimen is numerically computed in order to check against the test determined result. As a continuation of previous reported work by Lee and Sun⁽⁴⁾ and Jenq, et al.⁽⁶⁾, the computational procedure for predicting the ballistic limit of two-step braided textile composite target basically consists of four phases: (1) determine the penetration criterion based on the quasi-static punch curves obtained from tests to characterize the major damage mechanisms (containing matrix cracking, axial and braider yarns failure and pull-out) and locate the termination of these mechanisms; (2) analytically model the elastic properties of 2-step braided composite based on axial and braider fibers and matrix material properties and the geometrical relationship for braided composites; (3) apply finite element code (MARC) to take into account for the structural stiffness degradation in order to fit the quasi-static punch (load-displacement) curves; and (4) simulate the dynamic impact test conditions with the proposed static penetration model in order to determine the velocity of hemi-spherical tip-ended rigid impactor when major damage mechanisms have terminated. The modified Hertz contact law⁽¹⁰⁾ is used to model the contact force exerted on the 2-step braided composite target and penetrator with a specific incident velocity. An anisotropic elastic relation which provides stiffness degradation for

each unit cell of braided textile composite corresponding to proposed penetration criteria and the mentioned modified Hertz contact law are both utilized in the MARC finite element analysis as the user supplied subroutines. Friction is not incorporated into finite element analysis, however, an energy balance consideration is used to account for the frictional resistance in order to determine the projectile's residual (or terminal) velocity for complete perforation. The ballistic limit can then be subsequently calculated for given incident and the corresponding computed residual velocities.

Before performing the transient analysis of two-step braided textile composite target struck by a hemi-spherical tip-ended projectile, the static analysis using MARC finite element code is performed to simulate the quasi-static punch test conditions. A total of 108 meshes on the x-y plane is employed for the quarter plate due to symmetry and 432 elements (four layers in the thickness direction) are used to perform the numerical analysis for this quarter composite target. Specimen's meshes are characterized by three different sets of material properties corresponding to unit cells 1, 2 and 4 in order to account for the unique architecture of two-step braided specimen studied. The 8-node isoparametric element (element type 7 of MARC program) is used. The numerical simulated static punch curve is presented in Figure 1 as the solid curve, and good correlation between the test findings and simulated result is reported. According to the extent of damage observed from test samples, specimens are divided into (1) the extensively inner damaged region, (2) the secondary damaged region, and (3) the outer damaged region as shown in Figure 4(a). Figure 4(b) shows the extended major damage zone, the secondary damaged zone and the outer damaged zone used for numerical analysis when impact velocity is higher than 110 m/sec to account for the enlarged damaged pattern found from dynamic impact tests. A plot of the simulated fiber and matrix degradation parameters for inner, secondary and outer damaged zones versus displacement is to be presented in a separate paper⁽¹⁴⁾. After checkpoint E, the projectile started to exit from the distal surface of target, and a nearly constant friction force is observed from the punch test curves. Aforementioned procedures are proposed to serve as a guideline for subsequent impact dynamic analysis and the validity is to be justified by the agreement between experimental findings and the simulated results.

Transient analysis of impact system is then numerically analyzed. Initially, the incident velocity of the projectile is specified and the target is assumed to be stress-free and stationary. The simple displacement criteria are proposed to characterize the impact damage process: (1) If the displacement of impactor is loaded to check point A (i.e. $S_A = 4.59$ mm) shown in the static punch curve, the elastic moduli of matrix in inner, secondary and outer damaged region of braided specimen are degraded to the values determined from the fitted results of the static punch simulation described. (2) At checkpoint B (i.e. $S_B = 9.75$ mm), the fibers in the specimen start to break. When the target is further loaded along loading path CD and DE, the elastic moduli of fiber and matrix for these three damaged regions are continuously degraded according to the fitted results obtained from the static punch simulation to account for the extensive damage mechanisms containing both matrix and fiber breakage. Note that the corresponding displacements (i.e. S_C and S_D) for checkpoint C and D is 13.93 and 15.0 mm, respectively. (3) When the specimen is continuously loaded to a displacement level (i.e. $S_E = 18.0$ mm) corresponding to checkpoint E, the specimen is modeled to be on the verge of perforation and the finite element code simulation is then terminated.

The numerically computed final velocity of the projectile, corresponding to checkpoint E, is then used to calculate the residual velocity (V_r) of projectile based on energy balance consideration

$$E_r = \frac{1}{2} m_p V_r^2 = \frac{1}{2} m_p V_E^2 - F_E b, \quad (1)$$

where b represents for the length of projectile, and V_E and F_E are the projectile velocity and the steady friction force corresponding to checkpoint E and the frictional loading path beyond point E, respectively. Knowing the projectile residual velocity (V_r) from equation (1) for the specific incident velocity (V_s), the predicted ballistic limit (V_{BL}) can be calculated correspondingly.

A series of impact test simulations (run no. sbs01 to sbs06) is performed for projectiles striking with velocity ranging from 70 to 180 m/sec. Note that the static elastic properties for unit cell one, two and four are used as the input data. The predicted ballistic limit (shown in Table 4) increases as the incident velocity of impactor increases, since the major impact damaged zone increases for higher impact velocity condition. This trend is similar to that found from impact tests as shown in Table 3. Figure 5 shows a plot of projectile incident velocity (V_s) versus terminal velocity (V_r). For an incident velocity of 70 m/sec, the simulated terminal velocity is 12.53 m/sec, and this

means that target is perforated. Curve A in Figure 5 corresponds to those simulations utilizing static elastic properties. This curve intersects with the x-axis (i.e. zero terminal velocity) at an incident velocity near 65 m/sec, which is below the test determined ballistic limit of 74.1 m/sec. In addition, if we compare the triangular points which represent for test result with curve A in Figure 5, the simulated result seems to overestimate the test determined projectile terminal velocity. This discrepancy may be due to the following reasons: (1) the proposed static penetration model for two-step braided composites incorporated in the transient finite element analysis is unable to closely predict the dynamic impact response; or (2) the high strain-rate effect^(11,12,13) on the variation of the dynamic elastic properties of glass/epoxy braided structure needs to be considered in the numerical simulations.

Previously reported paper for predicting the ballistic limit for glass/epoxy plain woven laminated targets⁽⁶⁾ showed that the simulated projectile residual velocity and the corresponding ballistic limit becomes closer to those found from experiments when the dynamic elastic moduli (chosen to be two times the static values) are used as the input data in finite element analysis. Therefore, additional simulations (run no. dbs01 to dbs06) are furthermore performed using dynamic elastic moduli in the input data file in order to incorporate high strain-rate effect of target due to impact. In the current application the dynamic elastic moduli are chosen to be 1.5 times those of static values. The corresponding simulated terminal velocity and the predicted ballistic limit using dynamic elastic modulus degraded in the same trend as that used for run no. sbs01 to sbs06 are also presented in Table 4. Based on the corresponding simulated results shown in this Table, the ballistic limit should be close to 75 m/sec, which is quite close to experimental result (i.e. 74.1 m/sec). This can be observed clearly from the curve B in Figure 5 when terminal velocity approaches zero velocity. Furthermore, curve B seems to agree well with those impact test data points. However, for higher impact velocities (greater than 110 m/sec), curve B slightly deviates from the impact test result. Because the assumed extended damaged zones may be not very close to the test result. Nevertheless, it is concluded that the predicted ballistic limit for two-step braided is more close to that found from impact test measured result if we examine curve B in Figure 5 when the simulated residual velocity is near zero velocity. The averaged ballistic limit shown in Table 4 seems overestimates test determined ballistic limit due to the enlargement of major fiber broken damage area as incident velocity is increased.

CONCLUSION

The ballistic impact response of 3-D two-step braided textile composite plate struck by a hemispherical rigid projectile is reported. A series of quasi-static punch tests has been conducted in order to investigate the progressive damage modes of target and to obtain the punch load-displacement relationship and to characterize the penetration process to be used in the dynamic analysis. Ballistic limit is experimentally determined and the corresponding impact damage pattern is also reported. Numerical simulated result based on the static elastic properties of target seems overestimates the projectile exit velocities. When the target's elastic moduli used in simulation are increased by 1.5 times the static values, good agreement between the simulated terminal velocities and test results is found for projectile incident velocities ranging from 70 to 180 m/sec.

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Table 1 Basic mechanical properties of epoxy matrix and the axial and braider E-glass fiber yarns.

	axial yarn	braider yarn	epoxy matrix
Young's modulus	72 (GPa)	72 (GPa)	2.6 (GPa)
shear modulus,	29.5 (GPa)	29.5 (GPa)	0.963 (GPa)
Poisson's ratio	0.22	0.22	0.35
density	2,570 (kg/m ³)	2,570 (kg/m ³)	1,150 (kg/m ³)
linear density	0.0018 (kg/m)	0.0018 (kg/m)	---

Table 2 Geometrical parameters of the two-step braided fiber preform.

braider pitch length, h	0.01 m
aspect ratio of axial yarn, f _a	1
aspect ratio of braider yarn, f _b	5
packing fraction of axial yarn, κ _a	0.635
packing fraction of braider yarn, κ _b	0.635
number of axial yarn along specimen's width direction, m	13
number of axial yarn along specimen's thickness direction, n	2

Table 3 A summary of dynamic impact test result.

Test no.	Incident velocity (V _s)(m/sec)	Exit velocity (V _r)(m/sec)	Estimated ballistic limit (m/sec)	Change of energy ¹ (kgm ² /sec ²)	Change of momentum ² (kgm/sec)	Note
DB01	70.5	-	-	-	-	pp* with rebound
DB02	74.1	0	74.1	99.1	2.68	cp** and stuck on target
DB03	79.6	11.3	78.8	112.1	2.47	cp
DB04	99.6	53.3	84.1	127.8	1.67	cp
DB05	110.5	66.4	88.3	140.8	1.59	cp
DB06	114.9	73.8	88.1	140.	1.48	cp
DB07	132.2	95.3	91.6	151.5	1.33	cp
DB08	165.0	130.0	101.6	186.4	1.26	cp

¹ The change of projectile's kinetic energy is equivalent to $[1/2(m_p)(V_s^2 - V_r^2)]$

² The change of projectile's momentum is equivalent to $[m_p(V_s - V_r)]$

* Abbreviation 'pp' represents partial penetration

** Abbreviation 'cp' represents complete penetration

Table 4 A summary of the simulated impact test results.

Run no.	Incident velocity (m/sec)	Simulated residual velocity ¹ (m/sec)	Predicted ballistic limit ² (m/sec)	Note
sbs01	70	12.53	68.87	the static elastic properties were used in the numerical simulations
sbs02	80	32.3	73.2	
sbs03	100	59.5	80.4	
sbs04	130	96.7	86.9	
sbs05	150	120.6	89.19	
sbs06	180	154.77	91.91	
dbs01	75	- (rebound)	-	the dynamic elastic properties were used in the numerical simulations
dbs02	80	14.65	78.6	
dbs03	100	49.4	86.9	
dbs04	130	86.5	97.0	
dbs05	150	110.47	101.47	
dbs06	180	145.5	105.97	

Figure 1 Three typical load-displacement curves (dotted curves) measured from quasi-static punch tests and the numerical simulated curve (solid line).

Figure 2 Basic pattern of the quasi-static punch curves for two-step braided specimens studied.

Figure 3 The cross-section of the [12,4] braided specimen

Figure 4(a)

Figure 4(b)

Figure 4 Three-dimensional drawing of inner, secondary and outer damage zone in a quarter of specimen plate for dynamic impact analysis when the incident velocity is (a) less than 110 m/sec and (b) higher than 110 m/sec.

Figure 5 A plot of the striking velocity (V_S) versus terminal velocity.